

Micellar effect on protonation equilibria of L-arginine and L-histidine

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The protonation equilibria of L-arginine and L-histidine have been studied pH-metrically in varying concentrations (0.0–2.5%, w/v) of CTAB, SLS and TX-100 solutions maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ at 303 K. The protonation constants have been evaluated with MINIQUAD75. They exhibited a non-linear trend with increase in micellar content due to changed dielectric constant of the medium as well as electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces operating on the equilibria due to zwitterionic form of the ligands.

The protonation and metal-ligand equilibria of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid¹, oxalic and malonic acids^{2,3} were reported earlier in micellar media. Hence, the protonation equilibria of arginine (Arg) and histidine (His) have been studied in cationic (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB), anionic (sodium laurylsulfate, SLS) and non-ionic (triton X-100) micellar media.

Results and discussion

Plots drawn between the number of moles of alkali consumed per mole of ligand, *a* and pH (Fig. 1A and B) give information⁴ about (i) the number of moles of acid added, (ii) the sufficiency of the added mineral acid and (iii) the number and the pH ranges of the protonation equilibria. The values of *a* between -3 and -2 correspond to the volume of alkali consumed for neutralizing the mineral acid. The values between -2 and -1, -1 and 0, 0 and 1 correspond to the volumes of alkali consumed for the removal of carboxyl and the two amino protons, respectively. The arrows in these figures show the pH values corresponding to the values -1.5, -0.5 and 0.5. These pH values are the protonation constants of the amino acids. The protonation equilibria of Arg and His and the pH ranges of their existence are shown in Scheme 1. Overlap of the formation curves³ for different concentrations of amino acids rules out the polymerization of the ligands. The pH values at half integrals (2.5, 1.5 and 0.5) of formation function (\bar{n}_H) correspond to the log *K* values of the amino acids. These values are inputted as approximate protonation constants to MINIQUAD75⁵. The refined protonation constants along with the statistical parameters are given in Table 1.

The effect of systematic errors in the concentration of

Fig. 1. Secondary functions of protonation equilibria. Number of moles of alkali versus pH of (A) L-histidine, (B) L-arginine and formation curves of (C) L-histidine, (D) L-arginine.

ingredients like mineral acid, alkali and ligand was studied by introducing the errors in them. Results of a typical system are given in Table 2. The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of protonation constants due to incorporation of errors is acid > alkali > ligand > log *F*.

Effect of micelles :

The effect of surfactant on protonation equilibria and apparent shift in the magnitude of protonation constants in

Scheme 1. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of arginine and histidine.

micellar media compared to aqueous solution can be attributed to the creation of a concentration gradient of protons between the interface and the bulk solution⁶. Further, the micelles alter the dielectric constant of the medium, which has a direct influence on the protonation-deprotonation equilibria⁷. Because of the concentration gradient, changed dielectric constant, zwitterionic forms of the ligands and electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces operating on the equilibria, the variation of protonation constants exhibits non-linear trend with the mole fraction of CTAB (Fig. 2).

The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant and oppositely charged ions are concentrated in the Stern layer. Since CTAB has positive polar head, negatively charged ligand ions are concentrated in the Stern layer and hydrogen ions are pushed into the bulk solvent. Hence the protonation constants might have been decreased at the 2.5%, w/v CTAB concentration.

Table 1. Best fit models of protonation equilibria of L-arginine and L-histidine

In water-CTAB mixtures :

 Ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

% w/v	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	NP	U _{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ ²	R
L-Arginine (pH range 2.0–11.5)									
0.0	11.46(3)	20.67(6)	23.25(8)	88	23.21	1.88	10.90	74.00	0.024
0.5	9.76(9)	17.65(3)	19.21(9)	65	80.46	-0.78	3.40	7.35	0.044
1.0	10.39(4)	18.90(3)	20.30(5)	57	2.28	-0.80	2.68	17.70	0.007
1.5	10.48(2)	19.13(2)	21.01(2)	63	1.27	-0.89	4.75	8.35	0.005
2.0	11.10(2)	20.04(2)	22.10(3)	73	3.26	0.08	3.84	20.58	0.009
2.5	10.89(2)	19.64(3)	21.51(5)	73	6.95	0.11	3.76	6.55	0.014
L-Histidine (pH range 2.0–9.0)									
0.0	9.19(1)	15.11(1)	17.08(1)	63	0.83	1.18	5.38	12.29	0.004
0.5	8.86(1)	14.84(2)	16.92(3)	73	4.11	-0.96	5.02	23.75	0.009
1.0	8.79(1)	14.87(2)	6.76(3)	71	3.91	1.07	4.98	4.03	0.010
1.5	8.87(1)	14.85(1)	16.58(1)	69	0.81	0.54	3.47	3.80	0.004
2.0	8.85(1)	14.82(1)	16.49(1)	70	0.76	0.42	3.54	1.14	0.004
2.5	8.75(1)	14.71(2)	16.07(4)	68	3.20	0.42	2.94	8.24	0.009

In water-SLS mixtures :

L-Arginine (pH range 1.5–11.0)

0.0	11.46(3)	20.67(6)	23.25(8)	88	23.21	1.88	10.90	74.00	0.024
0.5	8.87(3)	17.26(5)	20.53(5)	176	57.60	3.04	10.62	560.77	0.311
1.0	8.84(3)	16.92(3)	-19.99(6)	157	21.76	3.54	14.50	459.30	0.183
1.5	9.90(3)	18.32(3)	21.20(6)	88	20.05	0.70	9.60	37.64	0.020
2.0	10.33(7)	19.28(5)	22.87(8)	88	17.38	1.57	4.69	22.18	0.015
2.5	10.42(5)	19.55(5)	23.56(2)	90	32.10	1.36	6.33	21.24	0.025

L-Histidine (pH range 2.0–9.0)									
0.0	9.01(1)	15.11(1)	17.07(1)	63	0.83	1.18	5.38	12.29	0.004
0.5	7.79(4)	13.32(8)	16.21(9)	106	52.84	1.55	6.10	62.42	0.029
1.0	7.44(4)	12.79(8)	15.31(9)	101	75.29	2.96	14.32	56.85	0.041
1.5	7.91(3)	13.53(5)	15.70(8)	85	24.36	1.12	7.47	29.25	0.026
2.0	8.73(2)	15.08(4)	18.34(6)	89	11.45	0.57	3.40	6.09	0.014
2.5	8.55(2)	14.72(4)	18.02(6)	90	11.65	1.41	6.09	18.22	0.014

In water-TX-100 mixtures.

L-Arginine (pH range 1.5–11.5)									
0.0	11.46(3)	20.67(6)	23.25(8)	88	23.21	1.88	10.90	4.00	0.024
1.0	11.20(2)	20.11(3)	22.18(3)	73	4.00	0.35	2.13	26.49	0.009
2.0	11.22(2)	22.14(3)	22.27(3)	71	3.79	0.67	3.14	3.58	0.009
3.0	11.48(4)	20.58(7)	22.75(9)	82	49.13	1.59	8.62	25.56	0.034
4.0	11.60(5)	20.74(6)	23.04(8)	60	13.51	1.11	3.95	8.93	0.017
5.0	10.83(2)	19.56(3)	21.64(3)	95	6.00	0.24	3.34	9.66	0.008

L-Histidine (pH range 2.0–10.0)									
0.0	9.01(1)	15.11(1)	17.07(1)	63	0.83	1.18	5.38	12.29	0.004
1.0	8.82(2)	14.65(3)	15.75(5)	53	6.38	0.23	2.68	14.90	0.013
2.0	8.98(1)	15.03(1)	16.80(2)	61	1.76	0.82	3.67	1.93	0.006
3.0	8.98(1)	15.00(2)	16.67(3)	59	2.55	0.76	2.94	8.37	0.008
4.0	9.25(6)	15.63(7)	17.64(8)	56	23.29	0.58	2.81	3.86	0.23
5.0	9.34(3)	15.90(7)	18.59(9)	77	22.85	0.44	2.58	14.21	0.022

$$U_{\text{corr}} = [U/(NP - m)] \times 10^8, NP = \text{number of points}, m = \text{number of species.}$$

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on protonation constants of L-arginine in 2.5% w/v, CTAB-water mixtures

Ingredient	% of error	log β (SD)		
		0 1 1	0 1 2	0 1 3
log F	0	10.89(2)	19.64(3)	21.51(5)
	-5	10.89(2)	19.65(3)	21.5(5)
	-2	10.89(2)	19.64(3)	21.50(5)
	+2	10.89(2)	19.65(3)	21.51(5)
	+5	10.89(2)	19.64(3)	21.49(5)
Alkali	-5	11.41(5)	20.55(6)	22.69(7)
	-2	11.08(3)	19.99(4)	21.96(5)
	+2	10.37(3)	18.78(4)	20.33(8)
	+5	10.69(2)	19.30(4)	21.05(6)
	-5	10.42(3)	18.77(5)	19.89(1)
Acid	-2	10.71(2)	19.31(3)	20.94(5)
	+2	11.06(3)	19.98(4)	22.04(5)
	+5	11.33(5)	20.51(6)	22.86(7)
	-5	10.84(3)	19.64(4)	21.66(5)
	-2	10.87(2)	19.64(4)	21.56(5)
Ligand	+2	10.90(2)	19.64(3)	21.45(5)
	+5	10.93(2)	19.64(3)	21.35(5)

Fig. 2. Variation of protonation constants with CTAB content. (A) L-arginine, (B) L-histidine: (○) log K₁, (Δ) log K₂, (□) log K₃.

The step-wise protonation constants of Arg and His pass through minima with increasing mole fraction of SLS. The amino acids have small hydrophobic groups and negatively

charged carboxyl groups at high pH. As SLS forms negatively charged micelles, it will compete with the ligands for the proton. Hence the protonation constants are expected to decrease. This is true up to 0.6×10^{-3} mole fraction of SLS. The subsequent increase in protonation constants may be attributed to the electrostatic stabilization of protonated ligand in cationic form by a strong anionic field on the surface of micelle.

Triton X-100 is a non-ionic surfactant which is expected to destabilize charged species, due to decreased dielectric constant. Since the amino acids at all the pHs have some charge. The protonation constants must decrease with increasing TX-100 content. The observed non-linear trend (Fig. 3) is due to (1) relatively less important electrostatic factors compared to non-electrostatic forces in non-ionic micellar media and (2) zwitterionic form of the ligands.

Fig. 3. Variation of protonation constants with TX-100 content. (A) L-arginine, (B) L-histidine : (O) $\log K_1$, (Δ) $\log K_2$, (\square) $\log K_3$.

Distribution diagrams :

Distribution plots of Arg and His obtained from the protonation constants of the best-fit models show the formation of LH_2^+ , LH and L^- from LH_3^{2+} . The zwitterion of Arg (Scheme 1) is present to an extent of 99% between pH 4.0 and 8.0 whereas for His the zwitterion is present between

pH 7.0 and 8.0. In agreement with the observations made in Fig. 2, it is found that the concentration of all the species have passed through minima with increase in CTAB content. Similar trends are observed in SLS and TX-100 media.

Experimental

Solutions of Arg and His (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. The purity of the surfactants (E. Merck) was checked by determining the critical micellar concentrations (CMCs) conductometrically. The CMC values for SLS, CTAB and TX-100 are 8.1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} , 9.2×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} and 0.54 vol%, respectively. The strengths of alkali and hydrochloric acid were determined by the Gran plot method⁸.

The alkalimetric titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying amounts of surfactants (0.5–2.5%, w/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} with NaCl at 303 ± 0.05 K. A Systronics 335 pH meter was used. Correction factor⁹ ($\log F$) to pH values was determined for each percentage of surfactant. The approximate protonation constants of the amino acids have been calculated using the computer program SCPHD¹⁰, based on formation function. Thus obtained protonation constants are refined by MINQUAD75.

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